

Trade-Off Between USBL Update Rate and Pose Estimation Accuracy in Factor-Based SLAM

Maximilian Popko*, Sebastian Bader*, Stefan Lüdtké*, Thomas Kirste* and Philipp Bannasch†

*Institute of Visual & Analytic Computing, University of Rostock, Rostock, Germany

{maximilian.popko, sebastian.bader, stefan.luedtke, thomas.kirste}@uni-rostock.de

†EvoLogics GmbH, Berlin, Germany

philipp.bannasch@evologics.com

Abstract—Accurate underwater localization and mapping is crucial for applications such as autonomous ocean exploration and environmental monitoring. However, due to environmental disturbances and poor visibility, underwater navigation remains challenging. Acoustic positioning systems, such as ultra-short baseline (USBL), address this problem with the downside of increasing infrastructural and energy costs. This study examines the trade-off between USBL update rate and pose estimation accuracy. We demonstrate that even infrequent USBL updates as sparse as once every 10 seconds can substantially improve localization performance when fused with inertial measurement unit (IMU) data and landmark observations through a smoothing-based Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) approach.

Index Terms—underwater SLAM, graph SLAM, acoustic positioning, underwater navigation, factor graph optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

The exploration and mapping of underwater environments remain challenging due to the ocean’s inherent uncertainties and scarcity of orientation points. Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM) is a crucial technique for underwater vehicles to navigate and build accurate maps. Traditional SLAM approaches rely on vision-based [1] or sonar-based [2] systems, but these methods often struggle with visibility constraints and environmental disturbances.

Monitoring the environment is an important task for creating digital twins of the ocean [3]. To overcome the challenges of underwater navigation, acoustic beacon networks such as narrowband long-baseline (LBL) or ultra-short-baseline (USBL) [4] are employed to obtain accurate positioning. However, these approaches come with certain drawbacks, as they require additional infrastructure, limit the operational range of the vehicle, and increase the energy costs of the system. Among them, USBL works as follows: a transceiver on the surface vessel sends an acoustic signal to a transponder on the underwater vehicle, which replies back, allowing the vessel’s system to estimate the vehicle’s position from the signal’s travel time and angle of arrival. Nevertheless, the underwater acoustic channel exhibits low bandwidth and suffers from high latency, resulting in position updates of lower frequency. Moreover, high velocities of the vehicle can further reduce the number of position updates and lower their accuracy. Optimal conditions can yield an update frequency of 1 Hz but can go up to every 10 seconds and more depending on the scenario [5], [6].

Fig. 1. How smoothing-based SLAM corrects past estimates given a single USBL position update leading to an overall more accurate trajectory. X and Y (East-North) coordinates of a 29-second-long trajectory. The start is at $[0, 0]$. A USBL position measurement of the vehicle occurs at $t=0$ and $t=25$. Landmarks can be detected at a frequency of 1 Hz. Yellow lines denote the vector (range-bearing) observation from the current position of the vehicle to the landmark. Green line depicts the filter trajectory, i.e. the maximum a-posteriori estimate of $p(x_t|y_{0:t})$. The red line depicts the maximum a-posteriori estimate of the smoothed trajectory $p(x_{0:T}|y_{0:T})$. Red ellipses represent the 95% confidence intervals of the marginal covariance of $p(x_t|y_{0:T})$. Z-axis (depth) is omitted (but calculated). Blue line depicts the ground truth trajectory.

Fusing sensors and observations to improve pose estimation is a key task in SLAM. Many techniques addressing the SLAM problem are available today [7]. Suppose the vehicle position and observation at time $t \in \{0, 1, \dots, T\}$ are denoted by x_t and y_t , respectively. Filtering-based SLAM, such as the extended Kalman filter [8] and particle filter [9], estimates the robot’s state by incrementally updating its position using only past and current sensor measurements, i.e., they estimate the probability distribution of $p(x_t|y_{0:t})$ for each t . In contrast, smoothing-based SLAM, like incrementally smoothing and mapping (iSAM2) [10], considers the entire history of sensor data $y_{0:T}$ to refine past estimates, i.e., it estimates the distribution $p(x_{0:T}|y_{0:T})$, leading to a more accurate and globally

consistent trajectory, as shown in Figure 1. This is mostly done offline due to being more computationally expensive than filtering based approaches. However, iSAM2 addresses this limitation by efficiently representing the problem as factor graph such that we can obtain the smoothing distribution at each time step.

While previous work presented how USBL positioning systems can improve the overall localization [5], [6], the impact of the varying update rates on the trajectory estimation remains scarcely investigated. In this work, we use acceleration and angular velocity data, landmark observations, and USBL position updates to estimate the pose of the underwater vehicle and landmark positions in both simulation and real world scenarios. We then investigate the trade-off between USBL position update rates and the accuracy of position estimates of underwater vehicles and landmarks. We make the factor-graph implementation publicly available¹, allowing the community to evaluate different scenarios and noise ratios.

II. RELATED WORK

USBL navigation systems are implemented in various filtering and SLAM approaches [11]–[13], due to their already proven localization-enhancing capabilities. These methods fuse the USBL data with traditional dead reckoning systems. The USBL measures the time-of-flight and the phase difference of the acoustic signal between the transponder attached to the vehicle and the transceiver installed on the surface vessel to calculate a range and bearing to the vehicle. Since these measurements are noisy, their respective uncertainty have to be considered. The USBL transceiver’s pose on the vessel can be tracked as a Kalman filter subsystem itself [12]. USBL is prone to measurement errors caused by low transponder elevation angles and changes in the vessel’s roll and pitch. The work of [13] addresses this by proposing an extended Kalman filter that dynamically adapts the measurement noise covariance. In their model, low elevation angles and platform tilting increase the uncertainty of angular measurements, therefore telling the filter, that these measurements are more noisy.

However, none of the before mentioned works, evaluate the impact of the USBL on the accuracy of the position estimation. Font et al. [14] provide a study that evaluates the Euclidean distance error of the filter trajectory using only odometry data and the filter trajectory fusing also USBL data. They show that using odometry alone results in a trajectory which continuously drifts away. Fusing odometry data with USBL corrects this drift, allowing a stable position estimate with bounded error. However, in contrast to our work, they do not provide a factor-based smoothing system that also considers landmarks as well as different update rates of the USBL to evaluate lower frequencies and the impact of correcting past estimates.

USBL has been used in factor-based navigation systems. The work [15] constructs a factor graph including USBL measurements and thereby solve the smoothing problem of estimating the whole trajectory given the observations. The factor graph models the problem as non-linear least squares

optimization task, which involves iterative solving due to refining linearization points. Doing this in an online matter would mean to solve the whole problem at every time step again. One of the most prominent methods that addresses this limitation is the iSAM2 algorithm [10]. Here, incremental, and consistent estimation is done by efficiently updating the factor graph and relinearizing only when necessary.

In this work, we use iSAM2 to solve the factor graph problem, which consists of measurements of an inertial measurement unit (IMU), landmark detections and USBL position updates, which are modeled as direct observation of the 3-dimensional position of the target. Various simulators for underwater scenarios exist [16]–[18]. For simple out of the box data generation, we use HoloOcean [16] which is an UnrealEngine-based simulator providing a simple Python interface making it easy to install and use across various systems.

III. FACTOR-BASED SLAM

Fig. 2. Example factor graph for $T=3$ and $N=2$. Grey variable nodes (x, b, l) are the latent random variables. Green, red, purple and yellow squared nodes are factor nodes and describe the likelihood functions. Note that this graph can be extended with further observations and therefore new variable and factor nodes.

The goal of the SLAM problem is to estimate the joint posterior probability distribution over the vehicle’s trajectory $x_{0:T}$ and the position of the N landmarks $l_{1:N}$ given observations \mathbf{y} , i.e. $p(x_{0:T}, l_{1:N} | \mathbf{y})$. The state of the vehicle $x \in (\mathbb{R}^3 \times SO(3) \times \mathbb{R}^3)$ consists of a 3D translation, a 3D rotation, which both together represent a rigid-body transformation in three-dimensional space, and a 3-dimensional velocity. The landmark l is represented through a 3D coordinate in the Cartesian world frame.

The observations $\mathbf{y} = \{\mathbf{o}, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{u}\}$ consist of measurements from an inertial measurement unit (IMU), i.e., acceleration and angular velocity data $o_t \in \mathbf{o}$, range-bearing detections of landmarks $z_{t,i} \in \mathbf{z}$, and USBL position updates $u_t \in \mathbf{u}$. Additionally, we model the time-varying bias b_t of the IMU, which affects the measurement of acceleration and angular speed, thus influencing the next state.

Each IMU measurement o_t , landmark observation $z_{t,i}$, and USBL update u_t is assumed to be conditionally independent of the others given the relevant state variables. Furthermore, not every time step t includes a landmark detection $z_{t,i}$ or a USBL update u_t . These measurements occur at times depending on sensor availability or detection success.

¹<https://github.com/mpopko/factor-based-slam>

The IMU bias b_t is generally modeled as a slowly changing process, and in practice, it may not be updated at every time step. For example, a new bias value may only be estimated every K steps (e.g., every 5th time step), potentially at equal intervals.

By recursively applying Bayes' rule, the joint posterior over the trajectory $x_{0:T}$, the IMU biases $b_{0:T}$, and the landmark positions $l_{1:N}$, conditioned on all measurements \mathbf{y} , and $K=1$, is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} p(x_{0:T}, b_{0:T}, l_{1:N} | \mathbf{y}) = & \quad (1) \\ & \alpha p(x_0) p(b_0) \\ & \cdot \prod_{t=1}^T p(o_t | x_{t-1}, x_t, b_{t-1}) p(b_t | b_{t-1}) \\ & \cdot \prod_{z_{t,i} \in \mathbf{z}} p(z_{t,i} | x_t, l_i) \\ & \cdot \prod_{u_t \in \mathbf{u}} p(u_t | x_t) \end{aligned}$$

The measurement $z_{t,i}$ refers to the observation of landmark l_i from pose x_t . We assume the correspondence of observation to landmark as given. The normalization constant α does not depend on the state $x_{0:T}$, $l_{1:N}$ and $b_{0:T}$, therefore it is not regarded in estimation.

Assuming normally distributed noise, the likelihood functions can be represented as multivariate normal distributions $\mathcal{N}(\cdot)$,

$$p(x_0) = \mathcal{N}(x_0 | \mu_{x_0}, \Sigma_{x_0}) \quad (2)$$

$$p(b_0) = \mathcal{N}(b_0 | \mu_{b_0}, \Sigma_{b_0}) \quad (3)$$

$$p(o_t | x_t, x_{t-1}, b_t) = \mathcal{N}(o_t | h_o(x_t, x_{t-1}, b_t), \Sigma_o) \quad (4)$$

$$p(b_t | b_{t-1}) = \mathcal{N}(b_t | b_{t-1}, \Sigma_b) \quad (5)$$

$$p(z_{t,i} | x_t, l_i) = \mathcal{N}(z_{t,i} | h_z(x_t, l_i), \Sigma_z) \quad (6)$$

$$p(u_t | x_t) = \mathcal{N}(u_t | x_t, \Sigma_u) \quad (7)$$

The functions h_o and h_z map the state variables to the space of the observations o and z , respectively.

The factor graph [19] is a bipartite graph $G = (\mathcal{F}, \Theta, \mathcal{E})$ with two node types: factor nodes $f_i \in \mathcal{F}$ and variable nodes $\theta_j \in \Theta$. Edges e_{ij} only exist between variable nodes and factor nodes. Consider the latent variables jointly represented by $\Theta = (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{l}, \mathbf{b})$ and every factor in Eq. 1 as $f_i(\Theta_i)$ such that,

$$f(\Theta) = \prod_i f_i(\Theta_i) \quad (8)$$

The subset of the variables that contribute to the factor f_i is denoted by Θ_i . Figure 2 depicts an example SLAM factor graph. The goal is to find the variable assignment Θ^* that maximizes $f(\Theta)$, which also corresponds to maximum likelihood estimation,

$$\Theta^* = \arg \max_{\Theta} f(\Theta) \quad (9)$$

Since all likelihoods are normally distributed, the following proportionality holds,

$$f_i(\Theta_i) \propto \exp \left[-\frac{1}{2} \|h_i(\Theta_i) - z_i\|_{\Sigma_i}^2 \right] \quad (10)$$

The objective function Eq. 9 can be written in non-linear least squares form [10],

$$\arg \min_{\Theta} (-\log(f(\Theta))) = \arg \min_{\Theta} \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \|h_i(\Theta_i) - z_i\|_{\Sigma_i}^2 \quad (11)$$

Here, $h_i(\Theta_i)$ maps the state variables Θ_i to a measurement, and $\|e_i\|_{\Sigma_i}^2 = e_i^T \Sigma_i^{-1} e_i$ is the squared Mahalanobis distance with covariance Σ_i .

To solve the non-linear least squares problem, note that if any of the measurement functions $h_i(\Theta_i)$ are non-linear, the overall objective cannot be minimized in closed form. In such cases, iterative optimization methods like Gauss-Newton are applied. These methods linearize the non-linear functions around the current estimate $\Theta^{(k)}$, leading to a linear least squares problem in the increment $\Delta\Theta$ at each iteration:

$$\Delta\Theta^* = \arg \min_{\Delta\Theta} \frac{1}{2} \sum_i \left\| J_i \Delta\Theta_i - \left(z_i - h_i(\Theta_i^{(k)}) \right) \right\|_{\Sigma_i}^2 \quad (12)$$

Here, J_i is the Jacobian of h_i evaluated at the current estimate. The estimate is then updated according to $\Theta^{(k+1)} = \Theta^{(k)} + \Delta\Theta^*$. The solution Θ^* corresponds to the maximum a posteriori (MAP) estimate, i.e., the most likely configuration of variables given the observations. Moreover, the system matrix formed by accumulating the terms $J_i^T \Sigma_i^{-1} J_i$ over all factors defines the information matrix, which captures the inverse covariance structure of the posterior distribution. The procedure is repeated until convergence. Further details on the construction of the Jacobian and optimization techniques can be found in [20].

Online factor-based SLAM incrementally adds a factor to the graph, which essentially results in re-estimating Eq. 12. The iSAM2 [10] algorithm addresses this problem by re-linearizing only when necessary and efficiently ordering the variables Θ using a Bayes tree [21]. This method is included in the GTSAM [22] library, which also allows for modeling the factor graph, i.e., the likelihood functions Eq. 2 to 7.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this case study, we aim to evaluate the impact of varying frequencies of USBL position updates on the estimation of the underwater vehicle's trajectory and the localization of landmarks.

Using the simulation environment HoloOcean [16], we generate noisy accelerations and noisy angular velocities via the IMU sensor at 60 Hz. Along the 3-dimensional self-driven trajectory, we add artificial landmark sightings. These landmark sightings consist of a landmark ID, a noisy range, and a noisy bearing measurement. At a given frequency, we obtain USBL measurements. We assume these measurements are already processed as 3D position observations of the vehicle.

Figure 1 shows the true trajectory simulated in HoloOcean. We use the library GTSAM [22] and its predefined factors to describe the conditional dependencies among the variables. IMU measurements are pre-integrated using the respective factor described in [23], such that we estimate the position

Fig. 3. Mean absolute error of the position, heading and landmark estimate of the smoothed and filtered trajectory under varying update rates of the USBL system. *No USBL* refers to the estimate only using the IMU data and landmark observations.

of the vehicle only once per second. We use the iSAM2 [10] algorithm for incrementally estimating the smoothed track given all measurements up to the current time point. The filter trajectory is obtained by taking the marginal distribution of the current state. Thus, the filter trajectory always represents the current estimate of the state. The smoothed track, in contrast, represents the joint posterior distribution given all measurements at the final time step.

The Gaussian sensor noise for acceleration has a standard deviation of $0.023 \frac{m}{s^2}$ and a bias distributed with a standard deviation of $8.2 \times 10^{-4} \frac{m}{s^2}$, and for angular velocity, a standard deviation of $0.00674 \frac{rad}{s}$ with a bias standard deviation of $4.85 \times 10^{-5} \frac{rad}{s}$. These values are in the range of typical IMUs. We update the bias every 5 seconds.

To evaluate the impact of the USBL update frequency, we vary the time between USBL updates from 1 to 20 seconds. The USBL data is a 3-dimensional observation of the vehicle's position in absolute coordinates (no orientation and no velocity information). This observation has a standard deviation of 0.25 meters in all three dimensions independently.

Object detections are simulated, and three artificial landmarks are placed around the trajectory, as shown in Figure 1. The vehicle has a forward-looking field-of-view with a horizontal opening angle of 120 degrees and a vertical opening

angle of 70 degrees. If an object is within that field-of-view, it is detected as a range-bearing observation. The range measurement has a standard deviation of 0.5 meters, and the bearing has a standard deviation of 1 degree horizontally and vertically.

We calculate the mean absolute error (MAE) between the estimated and the true positions of the vehicle under different USBL update rates. We also evaluate the MAE of the heading (yaw) of the vehicle and the MAE of the position estimates of the landmarks.

Next, we investigate a real-world trajectory of the Quadroin AUV by EvoLogics². This trajectory is 120 seconds long, and the vehicle had an average speed of $1.8 \frac{m}{s}$. Around this trajectory, we added seven artificial landmarks, and observations are generated with the same parameters as for the HoloOcean scenario. The noise parameters of the IMU are estimated by analyzing the standard deviation of the signal when the vehicle was steady and not moving. Generally, ground truth trajectories are hard to obtain in real world experiments, therefore, we use the output of the provided extended Kalman filter by EvoLogics as ground truth, which fuses the IMU, a Doppler Velocity Log (DVL), depth sensor, and a real USBL

²<https://www.evologics.com/robotics>

system with an update rate of 3 seconds.

V. RESULTS

Figure 3 presents the mean absolute errors (MAEs) for various state variables, comparing a simulated trajectory (HoloOcean) and a real world trajectory under different USBL update frequencies. Several key observations can be made:

We observe that smoothing consistently outperforms filtering for position estimation. This confirms that incorporating future measurements allows for retrospective correction of past state estimates, leading to overall improved accuracy.

In the HoloOcean simulation, higher USBL update frequencies lead to improved position estimation. However, even sparse updates—such as one every 20 seconds, resulting in only one to two updates over the entire trajectory—yield noticeable improvements. This trend also appears to be the case for the Evologics (real world) scenario, suggesting that even minimal absolute positioning information can significantly enhance the trajectory estimation.

The presence of seven added landmarks contributes to a well-estimated trajectory shape. However, due to reliance on relative observations and a noisy IMU, the trajectory tends to drift. This drift can be effectively corrected through even a small number of absolute updates, and smoothing subsequently propagates these corrections backwards the entire trajectory.

For the heading (orientation) estimates, filtering outperforms smoothing, and USBL updates appear to have limited impact. In factor graph-based state estimation, adding position updates and therefore only constrain the translation of the vehicle can unintentionally reduce yaw (heading) accuracy. This occurs because the optimizer compensates for position errors by rotating the trajectory to fit the USBL data more. The problem more strongly affects smoothing than filtering, since smoothing retrospectively adjusts past poses to minimize global error.

Regarding landmark estimation, we observe a similar behavior to that of the vehicle position estimation. In the HoloOcean case, high frequency updates significantly improve landmark localization, but even lower frequency updates enhance performance compared to having no USBL updates at all. For the real world trajectory, even a USBL update every 20 seconds leads to major improvements due to the absolute position observations of the vehicle which then again allows for correction of the landmarks because of the measurements being only relative observations.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this work, we explored the impact of USBL update rates on the accuracy of underwater vehicle pose estimation and object localization using a smoothing-based SLAM approach. We implemented a factor graph using GTSAM to describe the conditional dependencies derived from the SLAM problem and used iSAM2 as optimizer for finding the posterior distribution. Our results, obtained from both simulation and real world experiments, demonstrate that while higher USBL update frequencies improve localization accuracy, even lower update rates significantly enhance positioning compared to

IMU and landmark observations alone. We also observed that an absolute position update only once every 20 seconds can drastically improve localization if the shape of the trajectory is well approximated using relative landmark observations but affected by drift using inertial measurements. Since these results depend on the locations of landmarks and noise ratios of the sensors, we made the factor-graph construction and incremental inference pipeline publicly available; see footnote 1, allowing the community to evaluate specific scenarios.

Future work includes deploying the factor-based SLAM system in a live scenario to evaluate its performance in terms of computational efficiency and the approximation errors under tuning the hyperparameters of iSAM2 [10] for achieving real-time estimation. Additionally, smoothing-based systems offer improved accuracy for planning tasks, as new information can correct past estimates, enabling retrospective evaluation of the executed plan. For example, in an exploration task, a landmark observation that was already mapped, i.e. a loop-closure, can retroactively adjust the past trajectory, potentially revealing that a region was mistakenly considered explored. This capability enables more consistent and accurate strategies for *active SLAM* [24].

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research is funded by the German Federal Ministry of Research, Technology and Space (BMFT) as a part of the OTC-Rostock: Living Probabilistic Twins (OTC-DaTA2Model) project (03ZU2107CG).

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Zhang, S. Zhao, D. An, *et al.*, “Visual SLAM for underwater vehicles: A survey,” *Computer Science Review*, vol. 46, p. 100510, Nov. 2022, ISSN: 1574-0137. DOI: 10.1016/j.cosrev.2022.100510.
- [2] J. Zhang, Y. Xie, L. Ling, and J. Folkesson, “A dense subframe-based slam framework with side-scan sonar,” *IEEE Journal of Oceanic Engineering*, pp. 1–16, 2024. DOI: 10.1109/JOE.2024.3503663.
- [3] U. F. von Lukas, *Promoting digital twins of the baltic sea*, INFOS 2023 - Informatikunterricht zwischen Aktualität und Zeitlosigkeit, Bonn, 2023. DOI: 10.18420/infos2023-003.
- [4] P. Batista, C. Silvestre, and P. Oliveira, “Ges integrated lbl/usbl navigation system for underwater vehicles,” in *2012 IEEE 51st IEEE Conference on Decision and Control (CDC)*, Dec. 2012, pp. 6609–6614. DOI: 10.1109/CDC.2012.6426614.
- [5] E. Guerrero-Font, M. Massot-Campos, P. L. Negre, F. Bonin-Font, and G. O. Codina, “An usbl-aided multisensor navigation system for field auvs,” in *2016 IEEE International Conference on Multisensor Fusion and Integration for Intelligent Systems (MFI)*, 2016, pp. 430–435. DOI: 10.1109/MFI.2016.7849526.
- [6] Q. Luo, X. Yan, C. Ju, Y. Chen, and Z. Luo, “An ultra-short baseline underwater positioning system with kalman filtering,” *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 1, 2021, ISSN: 1424-8220. DOI: 10.3390/s21010143.

- [7] X. Zhou and R. Huang, "A state-of-the-art review on SLAM," in *Intelligent Robotics and Applications*, H. Liu, Z. Yin, L. Liu, *et al.*, Eds., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2022, pp. 240–251, ISBN: 978-3-031-13835-5. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-031-13835-5_22.
- [8] J. Sola, "Simultaneous localization and mapping with the extended kalman filter," *Oct*, vol. 5, p. 35, 2014.
- [9] L. Chen, A. Yang, H. Hu, and W. Naeem, "Rbpf-msis: Toward rao-blackwellized particle filter slam for autonomous underwater vehicle with slow mechanical scanning imaging sonar," *IEEE Systems Journal*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 3301–3312, 2020. DOI: 10.1109/JSYST.2019.2938599.
- [10] M. Kaess, H. Johannsson, R. Roberts, V. Ila, J. J. Leonard, and F. Dellaert, "iSAM2: Incremental smoothing and mapping using the bayes tree," *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 216–235, Feb. 1, 2012, Publisher: SAGE Publications Ltd STM, ISSN: 0278-3649. DOI: 10.1177/0278364911430419.
- [11] Q. Luo, X. Yan, C. Ju, Y. Chen, and Z. Luo, "An ultra-short baseline underwater positioning system with kalman filtering," *Sensors*, vol. 21, no. 1, p. 143, Jan. 2021, Number: 1 Publisher: Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute, ISSN: 1424-8220. DOI: 10.3390/s21010143.
- [12] Q. Luo, X. Yan, C. Wang, *et al.*, "A SINS/DVL/USBL integrated navigation and positioning IoT system with multiple sources fusion and federated kalman filter," *Journal of Cloud Computing*, vol. 11, no. 1, p. 18, Jul. 7, 2022, ISSN: 2192-113X. DOI: 10.1186/s13677-022-00289-3.
- [13] J. Ma, Y. Yu, Y. Zhang, and X. Zhu, "An usbl/dr integrated underwater localization algorithm considering variations of measurement noise covariance," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 23 873–23 884, 2022. DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3149831.
- [14] E. G. Font, F. Bonin-Font, P.-L. Negre, M. Massot, and G. Oliver, "USBL integration and assessment in a multisensor navigation approach for AUVs," *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 20th IFAC World Congress, vol. 50, no. 1, pp. 7905–7910, Jul. 1, 2017, ISSN: 2405-8963. DOI: 10.1016/j.ifacol.2017.08.754.
- [15] H. Qin, X. Wang, G. Wang, *et al.*, "A novel INS/USBL/DVL integrated navigation scheme against complex underwater environment," *Ocean Engineering*, vol. 286, p. 115 485, Oct. 15, 2023, ISSN: 0029-8018. DOI: 10.1016/j.oceaneng.2023.115485.
- [16] E. Potokar, S. Ashford, M. Kaess, and J. G. Mangelson, "Holocean: An underwater robotics simulator," in *2022 International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2022, pp. 3040–3046. DOI: 10.1109/ICRA46639.2022.9812353.
- [17] I. Lončar, J. Obradović, N. Kraševac, *et al.*, "MARUS - a marine robotics simulator," in *OCEANS 2022, Hampton Roads*, ISSN: 0197-7385, Oct. 2022, pp. 1–7. DOI: 10.1109/OCEANS47191.2022.9976969.
- [18] M. Grimaldi, P. Cieslak, E. Ochoa, *et al.*, *Stonefish: Supporting machine learning research in marine robotics*, Feb. 17, 2025. DOI: 10.48550/arXiv.2502.11887. arXiv: 2502.11887[cs].
- [19] F. Kschischang, B. Frey, and H.-A. Loeliger, "Factor graphs and the sum-product algorithm," *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, vol. 47, no. 2, pp. 498–519, 2001. DOI: 10.1109/18.910572.
- [20] G. Grisetti, R. Kümmerle, C. Stachniss, and W. Burgard, "A tutorial on graph-based slam," *IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Magazine*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 31–43, 2010. DOI: 10.1109/MITS.2010.939925.
- [21] M. Kaess, V. Ila, R. Roberts, and F. Dellaert, "The bayes tree: An algorithmic foundation for probabilistic robot mapping," in *Algorithmic Foundations of Robotics IX: Selected Contributions of the Ninth International Workshop on the Algorithmic Foundations of Robotics*, D. Hsu, V. Isler, J.-C. Latombe, and M. C. Lin, Eds., Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer, 2011, pp. 157–173, ISBN: 978-3-642-17452-0. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-17452-0_10.
- [22] F. Dellaert and G. Contributors, *Borglab/gtsam*, version 4.2a8, May 2022. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5794541. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/borglab/gtsam>.
- [23] C. Forster, L. Carlone, F. Dellaert, and D. Scaramuzza, *IMU preintegration on Manifold for Efficient Visual-Inertial Maximum-a-Posteriori Estimation*. 2015.
- [24] J. A. Placed, J. Strader, H. Carrillo, *et al.*, "A survey on active simultaneous localization and mapping: State of the art and new frontiers," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 39, no. 3, pp. 1686–1705, 2023. DOI: 10.1109/TRO.2023.3248510.